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Evaluations of Decision Support Systems in Urban Planning: Aksaray Inner Castle as a Case Study

Kentsel Planlamada Karar Destek Sistemlerinin Değerlendirilmesi: Aksaray İç Kale Örnek Olayı

ABSTRACT

Aksaray is one of the oldest settlements in Anatolia and offers a multi-layered cultural heritage due to its geostrategic location and long history of settlement. The Kaleiçi (Inner Castle) district, which forms the historical core of urban development, retains its importance with its castle and wall system, confirmed by archival documents, historical maps, and early photographs, even though its physical traces have largely disappeared today. Throughout history, this area has served administrative, commercial, religious, and educational functions and is the fundamental focal point representing the continuity of Aksaray's cultural identity. The necessity for contemporary conservation approaches to evaluate not only the physical fabric but also socio-cultural, economic, and morphological processes make Multi-Criteria Decision Making (MCDM) as an important tool. The Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) is widely used in cultural heritage planning because it can systematically determine the relative importance relationships between criteria. In this study, the AHP method was applied to Aksaray Kaleiçi; the area was divided into six sub-regions based on current use decisions, registered building density, and morphological characteristics. Five basic criteria obtained from the literature were evaluated: Urban Authenticity, Historical-Documentary Value, Cultural-Artistic-Aesthetic Value, Economic Value, and Urban-Formative Sustainability. Pairwise comparisons made by a group of ten experts on Aksaray and Kaleiçi were analyzed using the AHP method, and Urban Authenticity Value was determined to have the highest weight. This result shows that preserving the unique identity is a primary priority in conservation and planning decisions for the Kaleiçi area. The findings of this study provide a methodological framework that can be applied to similar historic city centers.

Keywords: Aksaray Kaleiçi; Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP/AHS); Multi-Criteria Decision Making, Urban Planning.

ÖZET

Aksaray, Anadolu'nun en eski yerleşimlerinden biri olup jeostratejik konumu ve uzun süreli yerleşim geçmişi sayesinde çok katmanlı bir kültürel miras birikimi sunmaktadır. Kentsel gelişimin tarihi çekirdeğini oluşturan Kaleiçi bölgesi, günümüzde fiziksel izleri büyük oranda kaybolmuş olsa da arşiv belgeleri, tarihsel haritalar ve erken dönem fotoğraflarıyla doğrulanan kale ve sur sistemiyle önemini korumaktadır. Tarih boyunca idari, ticari, dini ve eğitim işlevlerine ev sahipliği yapan bu alan, Aksaray'ın kültürel kimliğinin sürekliliğini temsil eden temel odak noktasıdır. Güncel koruma yaklaşımlarının yalnızca fiziksel dokuyu değil, sosyo-kültürel, ekonomik ve morfolojik süreçleri de değerlendirmesinin gerekliliği, Çok Kriterli Karar Verme Yöntemlerini (ÇKKVY) önemli bir araç hâline getirmektedir. Analitik Hiyerarşi Süreci (AHP), kriterler arasındaki görelî önem ilişkilerini sistematik biçimde belirleyebilmesi sayesinde kültürel miras planlamasında yaygın şekilde kullanılmaktadır. Bu çalışmada AHP yöntemi Aksaray Kaleiçi'ne uygulanmış; alan mevcut kullanım kararları, tescilli yapı yoğunluğu ve morfolojik özellikleri temel alınarak altı alt bölgeye ayrılmıştır. Literatürden elde edilen beş temel kriter değerlendirmeye alınmıştır: Kentsel Özgünlük, Tarihsel-Belgesel Değer, Kültürel-Sanatsal-Estetik Değer, Ekonomik Değer ve Kentsel-Biçimsel Sürdürülebilirlik. Aksaray ve Kaleiçi konusunda uzman on kişilik bir grup tarafından yapılan ikili karşılaştırmalar AHP yöntemiyle analiz edilmiş ve en yüksek ağırlığın Kentsel Özgünlük Değeri olduğu saptanmıştır. Bu sonuç, Kaleiçi bölgesine yönelik koruma ve planlama kararlarında özgün kimliğin korunmasının birincil öncelik olduğunu göstermektedir. Çalışma bulguları, benzer nitelikteki tarihî kent merkezlerine uygulanabilir nitelikte yöntemsel bir çerçeve sunmaktadır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Aksaray Kaleiçi; Analitik Hiyerarşi Süreci (AHP/AHS); Çok Kriterli Karar Verme, Kentsel Planlama

1. INTRODUCTION

Historic city centers are unique urban areas that embody cultural, social, and spatial layers from different periods of human history and possess high identity and memory value. Shaped by the accumulated heritage of different civilizations, these areas not only represent the past but also function as dynamic focal points that ensure the continuity of current urban life. Turkey is one of the countries with a high concentration of historic city centers due to its multi-layered historical fabric, archaeological heritage, and geographical diversity. Any planning, conservation, and intervention process carried out in these areas requires a balanced approach to multidimensional objectives such as preserving architectural values, sustaining cultural identity, meeting social needs, and ensuring economic vitality (Zakar, 2018). Current problems emerging in historic environments—intense development pressure, illegal interventions, destruction of the original fabric, unplanned tourism movements, population changes, transformation of trade, and economic sustainability issues—make it difficult to manage the conservation-planning processes of these areas using traditional methods. In this context, criteria must be considered not only in terms of physical structure but also in terms of socio-cultural continuity, economic viability, aesthetic value, and environmental sustainability. However, traditional planning and decision-making approaches often fall short in analyzing the intertwined, multi-layered structure of historic city centers; this can lead to the loss of unique urban identity, damage to cultural heritage elements, and the disruption of urban integrity. Therefore, contemporary approaches demonstrate an increasing need for multi-criteria and analytical methods in the evaluation of cultural heritage areas.

In recent years, Decision Support Systems (DSS) and, in particular, Multi-Criteria Decision-Making Methods (MCDM) have been widely used to establish an objective, scientific, and analytically evaluation mechanism in planning and conservation processes. These methods facilitate the determination of conservation priorities and enable the analysis of alternative scenarios in a comparable manner by bringing together assessments from different areas of expertise in a systematic structure. The Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) is one of the most widely used methods among these and offers high reliability, particularly in cultural heritage areas, in determining the relative importance levels of criteria. The AHP method transforms complex decision problems into a hierarchical structure, bases expert opinions on a mathematical foundation, and ensures that subjective assessments are analyzed within a rational system. This study aims to develop a scientifically based evaluation model to guide sustainable conservation and planning decisions in the Kaleiçi district of Aksaray, which forms the historical core of the city located in the center of Anatolia. With its multi-layered cultural heritage fabric, Kaleiçi, with its administrative, commercial, religious, and educational structures, forms the focal point of Aksaray's historical development. However, rapidly changing social and economic dynamics today make it difficult to preserve the region's unique identity, increasing the need for sustainable planning approaches. In this context, the AHP method was applied to address the study area holistically; the relative importance weights of the fundamental criteria guiding the area's planning, conservation, and adaptive reuse decisions were calculated.

The findings of the study reveal the fundamental values that should be prioritized in the conservation process of the Kaleiçi area; at the same time, it presents a scientific model that can be used in the development of sustainable conservation policies for historic city centers. In this respect, the study presents a comprehensive assessment approach that will contribute to decision-making processes not only in Aksaray Kaleiçi but also in other historic city centers with similar characteristics.

2. THE THEORETICAL BASIS OF MCDM IN URBAN PLANNING

Decision-making is a systematic process that aims to determine the most appropriate option from among multiple alternatives and criteria. In the literature, decision-making is defined as selecting the most appropriate behavior among those aimed at solving a problem and is considered a function that is future-oriented, involves risk, entails costs, and consists of specific stages at both the individual and organizational levels (Subaşı, 2011; Özdemir, 2019). Especially in areas such as urban planning, which involve multiple stakeholders, multiple criteria, and high uncertainty, decision-makers' intuitive approaches do not produce sustainable results; this situation increases the need for scientific methods. The decision-making process generally consists of the stages of problem definition, development of alternatives, evaluation, selection of the most suitable alternative, implementation, and monitoring of results. These stages demonstrate that single-criterion approaches are insufficient, particularly in multidimensional processes such as urban planning, cultural heritage management, sustainability, and spatial decision-

making. This is because decisions in such areas require the simultaneous evaluation of economic, social, environmental, and cultural criteria. In this context, Multi-Criteria Decision Making (MCDM) methods transform decision-making processes into a more analytical, objective, and comparable structure by providing systematic tools that allow multiple alternatives and criteria to be addressed simultaneously (Ulutaş, 2023; Koçdağ, 2013). MCDM encompasses the stages of identifying alternatives related to a problem, determining evaluation criteria, and calculating weights that express the relative importance of each criterion (Kaya et al., 2011). In the MCDM literature, decision-making problems are classified into three main categories:

- **Selection problems:** Determining the most suitable option among alternatives (AHS, PROMETHEE, TOPSIS, etc.).
- **Ranking problems:** Ranking alternatives from best to worst.
- **Classification problems:** Assigning alternatives to predefined categories (UTADIS, ELECTRE, AHPSort) (Özdemir, 2019).

Although the origins of these methods can be traced back historically to Benjamin Franklin's simple analysis method comparing positive and negative aspects (Şahin, 2014), with the increase in complex decision problems today, AHP methods have evolved into more advanced mathematical models. Intuitive decision-making is insufficient, particularly in multidimensional areas such as economic competition, spatial complexity, sustainability goals, and the preservation of cultural heritage; the use of analytical methods has become imperative (Koçdağ, 2013; Öztürk, 2005). The decision-making process in urban planning inherently involves a multi-criteria structure. Qualitative and quantitative criteria such as cost, social impact, environmental sustainability, preservation of cultural heritage, and accessibility must be considered simultaneously (Şahin, 2014; Tütek et al., 2012). In such a decision-making environment, MCDM methods offer decision-makers the opportunity to objectively compare and rank different alternatives and determine the most suitable solution. In cultural heritage areas, MCDM methods are widely used, particularly in determining reuse decisions, balancing conservation and use, functionalizing historical structures, evaluating aesthetic, ecological, and economic impacts, and comparing planning scenarios (Giove et al., 2011). One of the significant advantages of these methods is their ability to evaluate qualitative and quantitative data under the same umbrella and transform different expert opinions into a systematic structure. Furthermore, MCDM-based Decision Support Systems provide important contributions such as time management, data reliability, transparency, and repeatability in complex urban issues (Öztürk Aşan and Erdoğan, 2022). In this context, MCDM methods are considered indispensable tools for decision-making aimed at sustainable conservation and planning, especially in historic city centers. Consequently, AHP methods are powerful analytical tools that enable more scientific, valid, and rational decisions beyond traditional single-criterion approaches in areas such as urban planning, regional development, cultural heritage management, and sustainability, where there are multidimensional, conflicting, and difficult-to-evaluate criteria.

2.1. AHP (Analytic Hierarchy Process)

The Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) is a powerful analysis method that combines a multi-criteria evaluation structure with a systematic model for solving complex decision problems, converting comparative judgments into quantitative values. One of the most widely used models among MCA methods, AHP produces effective results, particularly in planning problems where quantitative and qualitative criteria are considered together, expert opinion is critical, and the decision process is multidimensional (Uzun and Kazan, 2016). Although the theoretical basis of AHP is based on the comparative evaluation logic proposed by Myers and Alpert in 1968, the systematic modeling of the method and its application to decision-making problems was carried out by Thomas L. Saaty in the 1970s (Yaralıoğlu, 2001). Today, AHP is applied in many different disciplines, such as sustainability, regional planning, cultural heritage management, business strategies, environmental impact assessments, and urban planning. One of the key features that distinguishes AHP from other MCDM methods is its ability to convert qualitative criteria and intuitive judgments into a mathematical structure, thereby making the decision-maker's internal evaluations analytical. In this context, AHP offers a system based on hierarchical model construction where numerical equivalents of subjective judgments can be generated (Kurttila, 2000; Lee & Walsh, 2010).

The AHP method is based on three fundamental principles (Güleç Korumaz, 2015; Uzun and Kazan, 2016):

1. Hierarchical Modeling: The decision problem is structured hierarchically, with the objective at the top, criteria and sub-criteria at the middle levels, and alternatives at the bottom. This model allows the decision maker to analyze the problem by breaking it down into its components.

2. Comparative Evaluation: Criteria and alternatives are evaluated through pairwise comparisons. Based on Saaty's (2003) 1–9 scale, these comparisons enable the creation of matrices that determine the relative importance of each criterion.

3. Prioritization and Consistency: The weights obtained as a result of the comparisons form the relative importance rankings of the criteria and alternatives. A consistency ratio (CR) below 10% is preferred; a low consistency ratio indicates that the decision maker's assessments are rational (Saaty and Özdemir, 2003).

The AHP method is generally applied in the literature according to the following steps (Kuruüzüm & Atsan, 2001; Uzun & Kazan, 2016): The Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) consists of a series of sequential steps for the systematic solution of decision-making problems. In the first stage, the objective of the problem is clearly defined; evaluation criteria, sub-criteria, and alternatives are determined and placed in a hierarchical model. After creating this structure, pairwise comparison matrices based on a scale of 1–9 are prepared to express the relative importance of each criterion compared to other criteria. Based on the comparison matrices obtained, weight values (priority coefficients) for the criteria are calculated, thus forming the fundamental quantitative components of the decision-making process. In the next stage, the Consistency Ratio (CR) is calculated to measure the consistency of the evaluations made, and if the CR value is less than 0.10, the comparisons are considered consistent. In the final stage, the criterion weights and the performance values of the alternatives are integrated to form the final decision, and the most suitable alternative is determined objectively.

2.2. The Role of AHP in Urban Planning and Cultural Heritage Fields

AHP provides significant advantages, particularly in multi-criteria and multi-stakeholder areas such as urban planning, sustainability, and cultural heritage management. Urban planning has a complex structure that requires addressing economic, environmental, social, and cultural dimensions simultaneously. Therefore, decision-makers are often faced with conflicting criteria. In this complex environment, AHP:

- Objectively weighting criteria,
- Systematically analyzes expert opinions,
- Making different scenarios comparable,
- Incorporating sustainable planning principles into decision-making processes (Giove et al., 2011).

In cultural heritage areas, AHP has a wide range of applications, including the repurposing of structures, balancing conservation and use, risk analysis, prioritizing sustainability criteria, and comparing planning alternatives. AHP's systematic approach provides decision-makers with a scientific basis, particularly for identifying unique values and determining priority areas for intervention. AHP is an effective MCDM method widely used in urban planning and cultural heritage management because it can analyze both qualitative and quantitative criteria within a holistic framework, convert experts' intuitive assessments into a mathematical structure, and bring a high degree of transparency to decision-making processes. 's AHP model, which integrates with the decision-making theory and MCA approaches discussed in previous sections, makes significant contributions to the scientific development of sustainable decisions, particularly in historic city centers.

3. FIELD STUDY: THE CASE OF AKSARAY KALEİÇİ (INNER CASTLE)

The physical development plan of Aksaray city center, which can still be discerned today, is determined by the traces of the circular-planned castle structure known to have surrounded the city throughout history but which has largely disappeared today. Records found in archival documents, accounts from early researchers, maps from the 19th and 20th centuries, and especially aerial photographs from 1954 reveal that this circular form is strongly reflected in the city's morphology. With a diameter of approximately 430–440 meters, the castle played an important role in the historical development of Aksaray as both a defensive and administrative center. Although Evliya Çelebi's Travelogue mentions that there were five gates in the castle, modern research and archaeological assessments indicate that there were four gates. These gates, named Konya Gate, Ereğli Gate, Meydan Gate, and Küçük Gate, are important focal points that shaped the city's transportation and trade routes during different periods (Topal, 2009; Deniz, 2015).

Data on the locations of these gates, thanks to descriptions in travelogues and traces preserved on old maps, form a fundamental reference source for understanding the morphology of today's squares and streets.

The Kaleiçi district has maintained its status as a center where administrative, religious, educational, and commercial functions have been concentrated throughout history; it has a multi-layered settlement fabric that carries the city's socio-cultural memory. Today, monumental and administrative structures representing the city's identity, such as the Government House, Great Mosque, Public Library, and City Hall, are located in this district. These structures play an important role both as concrete representatives of historical continuity and as focal points that sustain the city's current administrative functioning. In addition, the commercial functions concentrated in and around the Covered Bazaar demonstrate that the area is still the economic heart of the city. The bazaar area, in particular, bears traces of the traditional commercial fabric and serves as a center of attraction that creates continuity in both the daily practices of the local population and the urban memory. In this respect, Kaleiçi continues to function as a historical backbone where the city's administrative, economic, and religious functions intersect, despite the pressures of modern urbanization.

Another element that strengthens the historical continuity of the region is the Seljuk-era bridges located on the Ulu Irmak River. These bridges are not only infrastructure elements that facilitate transportation, but also important architectural structures that reflect Aksaray's urban planning approach during the Seljuk period. The spatial relationship between the location of the bridges and the castle form provides critical information for understanding the historical topography of the region. The proximity of the Seljuk bridges to the castle reveals the historical pattern of settlement habits shaped around both trade routes and water sources. Thus, both the castle and the bridges are considered elements that emphasize the spatial integrity of Aksaray's historical core. In conclusion, the Aksaray Kaleiçi region presents a multi-layered cultural heritage area with its historical urban form defined by circular castle traces, monumental structures, commercial centers, and Seljuk-era infrastructure elements. Therefore, the region is an important historical city center that must be preserved and sustainably transferred to future generations (Figures 1-2).

Figure 1. Aksaray Kaleiçi Region Registered Buildings (Parcel Query, t.y.)

Figure 2. Areas Studied

1. Region: The first of the six sub-regions defined in Kaleiçi contains two important structures representing historical and cultural continuity. The most characteristic structure of this region, **the Great Mosque**, was built between 1155 and 1409 during the Anatolian Seljuk and Karamanid Beylik periods and is one of the earliest and most monumental architectural examples in the region (Figures 3-4). Thanks to its multi-layered construction phases, original architectural decorations, and its location on an urban scale, it reflects both the historical development of Aksaray and the religious-architectural character of the period. **The Provincial Public Library**, located in the same area, was built between 1924 and 1926 and is an important public building representing the modernization discourse of the Early Republican Period. The library structure and its accompanying park layout demonstrate the importance given to the production of public spaces in the urbanization policies of the period; in this respect, it creates a unique historical environment where layers from the Seljuk, Beylik, and Republican periods can be read together.

Figure 3. Zoning plan (Aksaray Municipality, 2024)

Figure 4. Ulu Mosque and Provincial Public Library Building

2. Area: The second area of Kaleiçi is significant as a public center, as it contains a series of administrative buildings reflecting the institutionalization approach of the Early Republican Period. The most prominent structure in this district, **the Provincial Government Building**, was constructed between 1927 and 1929 and represents the architectural language of the early Republic and the reflection of the central administrative organization in the urban space (Figures 5-6). Another structure supporting the bureaucratic organization of the same period as the Government House is the **Provincial Gendarmerie Building**. Built between 1929 and 1930 and currently used as the Governorate Annex Building, this structure is important in terms of showing the spatial counterparts of the security and administrative functions of the period. Another public building in the area, **the Finance Building**, is part of the administrative structure of the Republican Era and has survived to the present day thanks to reconstruction work carried out in 1984–1985. When these three structures are evaluated together, it is seen that they form an administrative axis that transfers the institutional identity of the Republic to the urban fabric of the region; Kaleiçi is an important sub-region that bears the spatial traces of modern state organization within its historical layers.

Figure 5. Regional Development Plan (Aksaray Mun., 2024)

Figure 6. Government House (Özer, 2025)

3rd District: The third district of Kaleiçi has been home to structures that have held significant importance for the city's commercial and economic functioning throughout history. The most notable historical structure in the district is the Seljuk Han (Pamuk Han), known to have been built during the Seljuk period in the 12th–13th centuries. As an important part of the Anatolian Seljuk trade network, this han was among the structures that supported both regional and international trade passing through Aksaray. Although it has not survived to the present day (Figures 7-8), historical sources and archival records show that this han was an element that strengthened the commercial identity of the region in terms of both its location and architectural qualities. Today, the area where Pamuk Han was located and its surroundings have been repurposed with **the Municipal Business Center (MEDAŞ)**, which reflects the city's current commercial life, and various commercial units in the immediate vicinity. This transformation is significant in that it demonstrates how the historical commercial fabric continues to exist within today's economy with different functions. The coexistence of the traces of a lost Seljuk-era commercial structure in memory and the modern urban commercial cluster constitutes a clear example of the region's multi-layered structure, making the historical continuity and transformation of Kaleiçi spatially visible.

Figure 7. Urban Site Plan (Aksaray Mun., 2024)

Figure 8. Municipal Office Building in the Area (Aksaray Mun. 2020)

4. Area: The fourth area of Kaleiçi, which encompasses the Covered Bazaar and its surroundings, is one of the areas where Aksaray's historical commercial fabric is most intensely preserved, given its status as an **Urban Conservation Area**. The area is located on a total of **15 blocks** and has a street layout with a strong conceptual integrity. The streets forming the bazaar are planned in a linear arrangement, intersecting at right angles and ranging from **6 to 10 meters in width** (Figures 9-10). This layout reflects the rational bazaar typology commonly seen in the formation of commercial spaces during both the Ottoman and early Republican periods. The area consists of **approximately 200 parcels of varying sizes**, most of which house traditional commercial functions, craft workshops, and small-scale shops. The dense parcel structure and regular street layout demonstrate that the Grand Bazaar was historically the center of the city's economic life; it also forms the spatial basis for the area's continued commercial vitality today. With these characteristics, the fourth district presents a multi-layered example of urban fabric that represents both a cultural heritage value that must be preserved and the continuity of urban commerce.

Figure 9. Urban Site Area and Zoning Plan (Aksaray Mun., 2024)

Figure 10. Historical Bazaar in the Area (Özer, 2022)

5. Area: The fifth area of Kaleiçi, located **south of the Great Mosque and park area**, opposite the second area, represents an urban section where the historical commercial-residential fabric has undergone significant transformation today. While the district has traditional civil architectural fabric with small-scale residences and commercial units intermingled, it is currently being restructured as part of a recent **urban transformation project** (Figure 11-12). This transformation process is significantly altering the existing spatial character of the area; the traditional parcel structure, street scale, and historical fabric features are being replaced in places by modern development trends. Due to its location integrated with the historical core around the Ulu Mosque, this transformation of the area is of critical importance in terms of both spatial integrity and cultural continuity. The transformation of this area, which functions as a transition zone between the historic center and the administrative axis of the Republican era, produces multi-layered effects that must be considered in the context of urban identity, local character, and spatial continuity. Therefore, the fifth district is considered a dynamic urban transformation area that both carries traces of the historical commercial-residential fabric and is being reshaped in line with current planning decisions.

Figure 11. Urban Site Area and Zoning Plan (Aksaray Mun., 2024)

Figure 12. Urban Transformation Construction (2024)

6th District: The sixth district of Kaleiçi encompasses **the City Hall and its immediate surroundings**, featuring a mixed-use urban fabric that today predominantly combines commercial and residential functions. This district holds a significant position in Kaleiçi's current spatial organization, both in terms of its relationship with the administrative center and the continuity of commercial activity. The presence of the City Hall makes the district an administrative focal point, while the commercial units and residential areas surrounding it ensure that the district remains vibrant in terms of both daily life and economic activity (Figures 13-14). However, the **fact that future urban transformation projects are anticipated** in planning studies for the area indicates that the existing spatial character is open to change. Considering the area's integrated structure with the historical center, this transformation has the potential to create critical impacts in terms of urban identity and spatial continuity. In particular, the coexistence of the traditional commercial fabric and modern residential areas highlights the multi-layered structure of the area, emphasizing the importance of approaching the planned transformation process with a sensitive, sustainable, and locally identity-supporting approach. In this regard, the sixth district is considered one of Kaleiçi's dynamic and strategic sub-districts in terms of both its current functions and future planning objectives.

Figure 13. District Zoning Plan - 2023 (Aksaray Mun. 2023)

Figure 14. Municipality and its surroundings (Özer, 2024)

3.1. Evaluation of the Urban Conservation Quality of Aksaray Kaleiçi Using the AHP Method

Within the scope of this study, the historic city center of Aksaray Kaleiçi was divided into six separate zones in accordance with urban conservation principles, taking into account existing usage functions, conservation zone boundaries, density of registered structures, continuity of street fabric, and morphological integrity. This classification was made in order to analyze the multi-layered historical structure of the region in more detail and to evaluate the processes of spatial change and transformation with objective data. The historical building stock of each zone was examined in detail; the period characteristics, architectural qualities, levels of authenticity, and current physical conditions of the buildings were analyzed comparatively. In addition, street fabrics, the traditional parceling system, pedestrian and commercial axes, and spatial relationships were evaluated; the effects of changes in zoning plans on regional morphology were revealed in detail. Thus, both the elements of historical continuity that need to be preserved and the current conservation issues of areas under pressure for transformation have been identified. In line with these comprehensive analyses and taking into account the approaches

recommended in the literature for the value-based assessment of historical environments, the aim was to determine the assessment criteria that best represent the unique conditions of Aksaray Kaleiçi from among a large number of potential criteria. Prominent value classifications in national and international conservation literature, UNESCO and ICOMOS guidelines, academic studies on decision-making processes in historical areas, and expert opinions were examined comparatively; criteria that establish the strongest connection with Kaleiçi's unique structure, historical development process, cultural identity elements, and current planning issues were identified. In this direction, complex value sets were simplified and grouped under five main evaluation criteria within the scope of the study. These criteria both include priorities for preserving the historical and cultural identity of the region and form a scientific basis for sustainable urban planning and conservation decisions.

- Urban Authenticity Value (K1)
- Historical and Documentary Value (K2)
- Cultural, Artistic, and Aesthetic Value (K3)
- Economic Value (K4)
- Urban, Formal Sustainability Value (K5)

In order to establish a scientific and objective decision-making process, **10 experts** from different disciplines specializing in cultural heritage management, urban conservation, and planning in the province of Aksaray and its surroundings were selected. This group of experts consists of members of the Conservation Board, architects, urban planners, archaeologists, and academics, and has extensive knowledge of the historical, archaeological, and spatial characteristics of Aksaray Kaleiçi. The diversity of the experts ensured that the evaluation process was approached from a multidimensional perspective and increased the reliability of the decision-making stages. As part of the study, the experts were asked to evaluate the relative importance levels of **the five main criteria** in relation to each other using the pairwise comparison method based on **the 1–9 basic scale values** of the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP). These comparisons made by the experts formed the data set required for the operation of the AHP model, and the final criterion weights were calculated based on the analysis results presented in Table 1 and Table 2.

Table 1. AHP evaluation criteria (Lee and Walsh, 2010)

IMPORTANCE VALUE	DEFINITION	EXPLANATION
	Equal Importance	Criteria having equal importance
2,4,6,8	Intermediate values (Compromise values)	Intermediate Values
3	Slightly more important (Slightly superior)	The first criterion is more important than the other
5	Quite important (Significantly superior)	The first criterion is much more important than the other
7	Very important (Very superior)	The first criterion has a much stronger importance than the other
9	Extremely important (Definitely superior)	The first criterion has an absolutely superior importance compared to the other.

Table 2. AHP Method Decision Matrix to be filled in by experts - Step 1.

Criteria	K1 (Urban Authenticity)	K2 (Historical Documentary)	K3 (Cultural–Aesthetic)	K4 (Economic Value)	K5 (Sustainability)
K1 – Urban Authenticity	1		1-9 rating score		
K2 – Historical Documentary		1			
K3 – Cultural–Artistic–Aesthetic			1		
K4 – Economic Value				1	
K5 – Sustainability					1

The evaluation scores given by the experts for each criterion pair were combined using the **geometric mean** method as required by the AHP method, and a **pairwise comparison matrix (Matrix I)** was created based on these values (Table 3). The integration of expert opinions using the geometric mean ensured that different evaluations were consolidated into a single consistent matrix, reducing the impact of subjective interpretations and resulting in a more balanced decision structure. The resulting matrix enabled the relative importance analysis, one of the fundamental steps of AHP. The geometric mean calculations

performed on this matrix determined **the relative weights** for each of the five main criteria. Thus, the priority levels of the criteria in the decision-making process were quantitatively established using a scientific method (Table 4).

Table 3. AHP Geometric Mean (=GEOORT (Expert1- Expert10))

Geometric Mean – 10 Experts	K1	K2	K3	K4	K5
K1	1	1.25436	2.9026	3.7011	3.166208
K2	0.7972	1	2.9031	3.2363	1.718414
K3	0.3445	0.34446	1	2.0503	1.358341
K4	0.2702	0.30899	0.4877	1	0.496261
K5	0.3158	0.48774	0.7362	2.0151	1
Total	2.7278	3.39555	8.0296	12.003	7.739224

Table 4. AHP Geometric Mean Criteria Weight Section Table

Normalized Values	K1	K2	K3	K4	K5
K1 – Urban Authenticity	0.3666	0.369413	0.361484	0.308351	0.409112
K2 – Historical Document	0.292261	0.294503	0.361551	0.269634	0.222204
K3 – Cultural, Artistic, and Aesthetic	0.126301	0.101444	0.124539	0.170816	0.175514
K4 – Economic Value	0.099053	0.090999	0.060743	0.083314	0.064123
K5 – Sustainability	0.115785	0.143642	0.091684	0.167884	0.129212
Total	1	1	1	1	1

To ensure the validity of the AHP methodology and to determine whether there were any inconsistencies or contradictions in the evaluations made by the experts, all pairwise comparison matrices obtained in the study were comprehensively tested using **the Consistency Ratio (CR)**. In this regard, **the Consistency Index (CI)** was first calculated for each matrix, then this value was compared with **the Random Index (RI)** and consistency analyses were performed within the framework of the acceptance criteria proposed by Saaty and Özdemir (2003) (Table 5). According to the relevant criteria, for a matrix to be considered reliable and consistent, its CR must be **below 0.10**. The analysis results showed that the consistency ratios in the comparison matrices for all criteria examined in the study were well below 0.10 and close to zero. This situation reveals that the evaluations made by the experts are systematic, consistent, and compatible with each other; therefore, the AHP process exhibits a high level of consistency as a whole. As a result, the findings obtained both confirm the methodological validity of the decision matrices and scientifically prove that the calculated criterion weights can be used reliably (Table 5).

Table 5. Consistency Analysis Table

TOTAL/W	LAMDA MAX	TE – Consistency Index	TO – Consistency Ratio (CR)	Criterion
5.0553426	5.036529469	0.0091324	0.008153899	K1
5.0818277	5.031826189	0.0079565	0.00710406	K2
5.0340896	5.015159011	0.0037898	0.003383708	K3
5.0121284	5.005693708	0.0014234	0.001270917	K4
4.9999259	4.999259047	-0.000185	-0.000165391	K5

Following the successful completion of the consistency analysis, the data obtained from expert evaluations were comprehensively processed in accordance with the AHP method, and a **Criterion Weight Ranking** reflecting the relative importance levels of the criteria determined for the entire Kaleiçi region was created. This ranking constitutes one of the most critical outputs of the study in terms of quantitatively revealing the impact of each criterion in the decision-making process. The final weight values calculated based on expert opinions indicate which criteria should be prioritized in the protection and planning processes of Aksaray Kaleiçi, thus enabling the multi-criteria decision-making structure to be translated into concrete results. This weight ranking is presented in detail in **Table 6** and provides a scientific basis for developing sustainable conservation policies for the region.

Table 6. Criterion Weight Ranking

CRITERION NAME	CRITERION CODE	WEIGHT SCORE	RANK
Urban Authenticity Value	K1	0.362	1
Historical and Documentary Value	K2	0.288	2
Cultural, Artistic, and Aesthetic Value	K3	0.139	3
Urban, Formal, and Sustainability Value	K5	0.129	4
Economic Value	K4	0.079	5

The results of the AHP analysis revealed that among the criteria guiding planning and conservation decisions in the Aksaray Kaleiçi area, covering six districts, the value of **Urban Authenticity** had by far the highest weight (0.362) (Table 6). This result shows that preserving the historical fabric, spatial organization, and unique settlement identity of the area takes precedence over all other criteria. The prominence of Urban Authenticity indicates that the unique character of Kaleiçi in physical, cultural, and

symbolic terms should be the fundamental determinant of sustainable conservation policies. The **Historical and Documentary Value** criterion (0.288), which follows Authenticity, shows that the preservation and evaluation of written and visual sources that shed light on the city's past play a critical role in understanding the historical continuity of the area. The third criterion, **Cultural, Artistic, and Aesthetic Value** (0.139), reveals that the region's cultural heritage, architectural expressions, and aesthetic integrity are complementary elements that must be considered in conservation processes. The **Urban and Formal Sustainability** criterion (0.129), which follows, emphasizes the importance of the area's long-term spatial resilience, morphological continuity, and environmental harmony. The **Economic Value** criterion (0.079), which has the lowest weight value, shows that although economic functions in the area are important, they are less of a priority than other criteria in conservation and planning processes. When this ranking is evaluated overall, it is seen that conservation policies in Kaleiçi should be based primarily on the sustainability of historical integrity, unique identity, and cultural values.

4. RESULTS

This study presents an analytical decision support framework for the conservation and sustainable planning of the historic city center of Aksaray Kaleiçi, located in the heart of Anatolia. Considering the multidimensional nature of conservation decisions in historic cities, the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) method was used, and a systematic analysis based on expert-based assessments was conducted. The fact that the consistency values obtained in the study are below acceptable thresholds indicates that the expert opinions are methodologically reliable and that the decision model has scientific validity. This supports the findings in the literature that AHP can be used as a powerful decision support tool in city centers with complex historical layers.

The AHP analysis results revealed that the value of **Urban Authenticity** holds a dominant position among the criteria determining the planning and conservation priorities of the Kaleiçi area. Preserving user experience, spatial integrity, topographic continuity, street-parcel relationships, and the historical morphology formed by castle traces requires a holistic approach that transcends the scale of individual structures. In contrast, the low weighting of the **Economic Value** criterion indicates that short-term economic gains should not guide decision-making processes and that sustainability should be approached as an integrated combination of cultural, spatial, and social values. These findings are consistent with the international literature, which emphasizes that conservation-oriented planning approaches are essential in historic city centers and may be incompatible with purely economic rationality.

In conclusion, the study demonstrates that the AHP model developed specifically for Aksaray Kaleiçi is a methodological tool that can be applied both locally and in other Anatolian cities with similar characteristics. The model brings together contributions from different fields of expertise within a numerical system, enabling conservation and planning decisions to be based on objective grounds. In this context, future zoning plan revisions, functionalization decisions, and design projects should adopt urban uniqueness as a guiding principle; policies and strategies aimed at preserving the historical street fabric, parcel structure, and traces of the castle should be prioritized. Furthermore, integrating the AHP approach with comprehensive decision support systems that holistically assess social, cultural, and environmental sustainability will significantly contribute to the long-term preservation of historic environments.

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Author Contribution and Conflict of Interest Declaration Information

All authors contributed equally to the article. There is a conflict of interest with Mehmet ÖZER and Mustafa KORUMAZ.

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